

Research

A survey on Literacy practices in adult literacy centers in Cameroon: The Mfoundi Department

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Abstract: *It became clear during the 1990s that adult literacy must be an important part of all strategies for development. It should be noted that the way literacy is practiced in literacy centers determine the efficiency of literacy programs. The aim of this survey is to know if literacy practices in the Mfoundi Department in Yaoundé Cameroon is in accordance with the expectation of learners. I used survey as data collection method. My survey took place in 5 of the seven districts of the Mfoundi Department; because Yaoundé I and Yaoundé VII have no literacy center yet. The survey was conducted in 29 literacy centers with a total of 656 respondents. As for the findings, I discovered that literacy practices does not really reach the expectation of learners, and also that learners are more interested in functional aspect of literacy than the classical aspect. By writing this paper, my main hope is that it helps to sensitize those in charge of literacy program, such as to make them pay more attention to the carrying out of literacy practices in literacy centers.*

Keywords: Cameroon, Literacy practices, Mfoundi Department

Introduction

Considering the importance of adult literacy in the well-being of a country's population, it is important for us to know how these adults are trained in the different literacy centers. To carry out this analysis we found it important to focus on a few strengths that are: 1) People involved, 2) Reasons why people are interested in the adult literacy program, 3) what the beneficiaries of the

adult literacy program in Cameroon think concerning the program, 4) the main disciplines offered by the adult literacy program in Cameroon, 4) the main disciplines offered by the adult literacy program in Cameroon, 5) Teaching time, 6) Teaching site, 7) Teachers, 8) Funding, 9) Pattern of teaching, 10) Quality assurance, 11) Implementation method, 12) Beneficiaries participation in functional literacy activities, 13) Some strategies to strengthen adult literacy policy in Cameroon.

First of all, the goals of adult literacy in literacy centers in Cameroon are:

- Empowering young people or adults through learning to read, write and basic mathematics in order to better their life;
- To fight against poverty by learning a new profession or by improving oneself;
- learn to read, write and calculate to integrate into the national community;
- better develop its activities for those who already have, since learning reading, writing and calculations now allows the beneficiary to have a slightly more varied field of reflection.

(**Source:** Politique Nationale de l'Alphabétisation, de l'Education non formelle et de la Formation en Langues)

I. People involved

People concerned by the adult literacy program in Cameroon are those who, during childhood, did not have the chance to attend formal schools, or those who have of course attended the formal system, but have not been able to continue education till the end for various reasons. Among these people we have women, men, youth, workers, non-workers... and sometimes people who have some mental problems, not allowing them to be admitted to formal schools. The only condition to belong to this group is to be at least 15 years old.

Adult literacy in Cameroon sometimes gives the impression of being something that concerns women much more than men (**Figure 1: Gender of participants**). All the literacy centers that I had to go through, I have noticed every time that the number of women is still well above the number of men found in the centers. There are centers in which there is not even one male person. Does this mean that the development aspired by Cameroonians will be possible only thanks to women, Does this mean that men do not need to learn to achieve development, so many questions are be asked. As we can see from the above graph and the table below, out of 656 learners who answered the questionnaire, 440 are women and only 216 are men. This

exactly in terms of percentage is 32.9% for men against 67.1% for women; more than double the size of men (**Table1: Distribution per gender**).

I went to a literacy center where I found only women and most of them came to class with their babies, which made the task a bit difficult for the literacy educator. When I was exchanging with one of them she let me know that she has friends who want to take part to the program for adult literacy but unfortunately because of the housework they cannot register and move on with other women.

It's true that there are also some men who really want to take part in the adult literacy program, but who actually do not have enough time to go and sit in literacy centers to learn because, according to them they are supposed to be outside struggling to take care of their wives and children. They would like the government to do something or think of solutions that can also enable them to join this program, which is of paramount importance to the country's development.

Among the 656 respondents 597 are workers or at least have a job that allows them to earn money for their survival. 59 respondents are unemployed, which means 91% of our respondents are workers and 9% unemployed (**Table2 (status of respondents): Are you a worker?**).

Among the workers, there are people who practice in different sectors of activity, i.e. for example in the governmental sector we register 36% of the members; we also have 9% who work for private sectors and then, we have the largest majority which is beyond 46% and are self-employed people, this is to say they created their activities themselves. (**Figure 2: Are you working for the government, private sector or self-employ?**)

It is important to remember one thing in this stage, which is, one should not always say that someone who works for the government or for a private company does not necessarily need to go to school to better his or her reading, writing and calculation skill. I use to think that way before, but I started to see things differently after my research period in Cameroon. At the first literacy centers where I went to conduct my research, I realized against all expectation that some people fill the survey pointing that they are workers, and then when choosing the sector of activity, I saw some mentioning that they work for the government or for the private sector. I was a little curious to the point where I approached a lady and then I asked the lady why she is already

working in government and then she is still enrolling in the literacy program. Once I asked my question, the lady looked at me and started to laugh and then she said, "My dear, I work for the government, but do you know what my work is all about? what I do on a daily basis is to get to work and then any newspaper agent that come to deliver newspapers, it's me who gets them and then I distribute them in all the offices while recovering those distributed the day before and returning them to where they have to be range. That's all I do as a job, that's why I came to retrain in the hope that I will finally acquire knowledges that will allow me to be promoted to a position better than the one I'm exercising now ".

According to what I have seen in literacy centers, it is a bit difficult for people working for the government or the private sector to be in school every day; contrary to those who are self-employed. They are better because they have the opportunity to manage or manipulate their time as they want.

Among those working in the private sector, we the category of those who work as domestic servants in private homes; and for this category of people, it is a bit difficult to attend classes normally, and to evolve with other learners; Because they always need permission from their boss, who sometimes refuses and it makes the task difficult for literacy educators.

II. Reasons why people are interested in the adult literacy program

Reasons why Cameroonians enroll in adult literacy programs are many and vary from one person to another. In the same group of persons for example, we can have people who follow the program just for personal pleasure, people who follow the program in order to find a better job, people who follow the program because they are bored at home, people who follow the program because they realize that they are failing to help children do their homework, people who follow the program just because they have friends who are enrolled in this program... As we can see, the reasons are diverse.

- Reasons why people are interested

Among the 656 people who completed the questionnaire and from 29 different literacy centers, 119 people said they were interested in the adult literacy program just because of promotion at work, 60 people say they interested in this program to improve their level of reading, writing and

math so they can help their children and grandchildren with their homework, because they say they are sad to see their children or grandchildren anxious because they cannot get help from their parents when it comes to helping them with their homeworks. 357 people say they are interested in the program so they can find a decent job that can help them meet their daily needs. 61 people, however, say they are interested in the program just for personal pleasure, in other words, they just want to learn to read, write and calculate to have fun. 59 people are interested in the program to acquire knowledge and no longer be on the sidelines of the scientific and technical progress that define the degree of education of humans today. (**Figure 3 : Reasons why people are interested**)

From these answers we can also deduce that the level of education plays an essential role in the acquisition of quality work in Cameroon. Of the 656 respondents, 357 say they are interested in the literacy program in order to find a decent job, which is more than half of those surveyed. It also allows us to understand that without education, the population can only engage in work that one would be tempted to call low-level work.

III. what the beneficiaries of the adult literacy program in Cameroon think concerning the program

As I said above, every person who goes to a literacy center goes with his own convictions and apprehensions. It is in this perspective that we can find in the same center people who have developed an attachment to the program and others who do not find their account and this for several reasons.

- Is the program interesting?

Out of 656 learners surveyed, 358 people find the adult literacy program interesting, 120 people find the program unattractive, and 178 people find that the program is just there; neither interesting nor bad. The observation we make at this level is that the vast majority gave a favorable response to the literacy program in Cameroon, not to mention that beside these there is the second majority which is in the middle of the scale, that is to say that they did not give a positive or negative judgment concerning the program. From this observation, we can understand that most adults in Cameroon are attracted to the literacy program (**Figure 4**). Although the

conditions are not always favorable for them to attend classes, they still have a lot of admiration and appreciation for the program.

Since there was a difference of opinion, I tried to understand why some people find the program interesting, maybe even very interesting, and some do not. I got the following results.

- Why do you find adult literacy program interesting?

Of the 358 people who found the adult literacy program interesting, 295 say that through the literacy program, they can now read, write and make small calculations; this allows them to help their children at home to do their class homework. 4 people said that thanks to the adult literacy program they are now able to express themselves using a language other than the mother tongue, and 59 people say that thanks to this program, they have been able to develop their activities. They had ideas but it was difficult for them to put these ideas into practice. Because of the literacy program and the little knowledge they have acquired, they have now been able to discuss and think differently about their sector of activity (**Table3**).

-Why don't you find the literacy program interesting?

Out of 120 people who find the adult literacy program unattractive, 119 say the program does not meet their expectations; and only one person says that she is not interested because she does not understand the courses (**Table4**). As for the understanding of the courses, I realized that the person in question is enrolled in a center where courses are conducted in French only, while she can only speak English. It is a situation that made me think about the problem of the language of instruction in adult literacy centers in Cameroon, and we will have the opportunity below to understand what learners think about the language of instruction in literacy centers.

IV. Main disciplines offered by the adult literacy program in Cameroon

When I spoke about the disciplines found in adult literacy centers in Cameroon, I thought much more about reading, writing and calculating. But once in the field I realized that the functional component is not negligible in literacy centers in Cameroon, because the majority of young people enrolled for this program think less about conventional literacy. They are much more

tempted by functional literacy (**Figure 5: What are the main discipline(s) your program offers? And Figure 6: Which discipline(s) do you prefer?**).

As we can see from **Figure 5** and **Figure 6**, there is an apparent imbalance between the disciplines that are taught in literacy centers in Cameroon and the disciplines that are preferred by learners. On the first figure, among the disciplines that are proposed we have reading, writing, calculations, communication and “others”, “others” that is to say learning a trade. The students or the learners in the first case have in majority chosen reading, writing and calculations as disciplines that are dispensed in their literacy centers (**Figure 5 : What are the main discipline(s) your program offers?**). When I speak of majority, I simply want to say that out of 656 students 298 have chosen writing reading and calculations, 60 are for writing and reading 177 for reading and numeracy, 60 for communication and the remaining 60 are for "others" ie learning a trades. But when we try to look at what learners prefer, we realize (**Figure 6: Which discipline(s) do you prefer?**) that there are 418 out of 656 people who prefer learning trades; only 60 people chose communication and 178 people are for reading writing and calculations. From those numbers, it is possible to say that policymakers do not take into account the views of learners when they want to develop adult literacy policies.

I was even tempted to ask them why they prefer X and not Y, here are the answers I got:

418 people think that the choice they made meets their needs, while 178 people made the choice, taking into account that they better understand what their choice is about, and 60 other people did not give specific reason for their choices, while saying that they choose what they choose, for other reasons (**Table 5**).

V. Duration of training and teaching time in literacy centers in Cameroon

Concerning the duration of training and teaching time in adult literacy centers in Cameroon in general, and in Nfoundi in particular, I find that, whether the duration of training, weekly session frequency or teaching hours per day, there is variability depending on the center in which one is. This is how I found centers on the ground that have a training period of 2 years, 3 years and sometimes even more. Similarly, there are centers that have existed for 6 months or a year and

then closed for reasons that may be financial or other such as lack of learners and sometimes also the wrong choice of the site. It should be pointed out that the adult literacy program in Cameroon and many other countries in the world depends first and foremost on the location of the literacy centers and also on the learning needs and aspirations of the beneficiaries, who generally go about their business and give themselves up to literacy activities only during the free time.

-How long have you being involved into adult literacy program?

By analyzing the table on the duration of involvement into adults program in literacy centers (**Table6**) in Cameroon, especially in Nfoundi Department, the observation is that, out of 656 respondents, 358 have being involve into the program for less than six months, 238 persons whose duration is between six months to two years and only 60 persons are above two years. From the first to the third one, the gap of progression is obviously decreasing. Between the first and the second stage, we can notice a difference of 120 persons, and between the second and the third stage, the gap is even bigger, 178. From the table, we can see that people are motivated to start literacy program but only few persons are ready to follow the program to the end. According to literacy educators, those who finish the program are mostly those who are not working because they have no constraints of permission from the employer before attending the class.

let us nevertheless point out that the normal duration of a literacy cycle in Cameroon is 3 years minimum (**Politique Nationale de l'Alphabétisation, de l'Education non Formelle et de la Formation en Langues**) but unfortunately we find that in our literacy centers, only the most persevering and as we saw in the table, in A very small number manage to complete their training cycle.

-How many time do you have classes per week?

Concerning the number of class per week, we can see that, out of 656 learners in literacy centers, 417 people in one week have literacy courses one to two times, 179 persons have classes 3 times and only 60 people are taught 4 times a week (**Table7**). This means that we have people in literacy centers who, in a whole year, school only 52 times, which is insignificant for a good

acquisition of reading, writing and numeracy skills. To attend at least 3 to 4 times a week, I think this time can at least allow a learner to acquire the skills necessary to achieve the goals he or she needs after a few years. It's unfortunate when we look at these data and, especially when we know that, Cameroon intends to develop and it cannot be achieved with an illiterate population. We have the impression that the better the solutions, the less the learners engage.

-What is the duration per class?

In table 8 (**Table8**), which deals with teaching time in literacy centers in Cameroon, we notice 3 compartments; the first, which states that the course lasts 1 hour, the second which stipulates that the course lasts 2 hours and the third which stipulates that the course lasts 2 to 3 hours. So the finding that we make is that, on 656 learners questioned, just 9% make up to 3h per class session; 45.3 for two hours and then 45.6 percent, which is the majority just one hour of class per day. The problem is not always linked to the literacy center. It also happens sometimes that learners even in the middle of the course are obliged to interrupt to attend to other occupations. I experienced the scene in a literacy center in which a young gentleman, a taxi driver came to class and few minutes later, a customer called him saying that he must accompany him to the airport, and as generally the price of the taxi to the airport is often high, so the gentleman was forced to drop out and go to work, and then when I asked him why he couldn't wait till at least break time, he replied that if he does not do it the customer will get another taxi and he will lose money.

Another problem I have encountered in literacy centers concerning teaching time is the availability of learners. The learners are not available at the same time, so the coach is often obliged to comply with schedules that can accommodate each other. For example, the majority of centers are obliged to lecture at night and sometimes in rooms with insufficient light. Admittedly, the literacy policy currently applied in Cameroon is that of decentralization, that is to say that certain competences have been transferred to the town halls for the management of problems related to adult literacy. . Following this decentralization, a decree was signed by the prime minister, head of the government, authorizing those in charge of literacy program to practice in all public primary schools in their district. But there is a problem with the fact that literacy instructors or learners are supposed to wait until the end of the classes of the children who

normally occupy these institutions before being able to occupy them in their turn; which means that the majority of courses are held in the evening and sometimes these schools are not always enlightened; This poses a problem of teaching time because the teacher sometimes finds himself obliged to reduce the teaching time, given that night is already falling. Although time is sometimes reduced, this does not prevent learners from arriving late.

VI. Teaching site

It is true that adult literacy activities in Cameroon are supposed to be held in public primary schools (**Decree Number 2016/1247 / PM. (May 23, 2016)**). But given some difficulties sometimes related to the disagreement between the heads of these institutions and the literacy instructors, these courses are sometimes relocated to other sites, which are sometimes not very comfortable for learners and even for educators. Given the limited financial means, neither learners nor literacy educators often have no other choice than to be satisfied with the space available to them. Literacy educators who have space in their homes prefer to build a small space at their place to help them with their activities (**Picture1**).

Literacy instructors who do not have enough space at their place are sometimes forced to go and rent someone else's space to develop their literacy centers. It is important to mention that these spaces that are rented are not always VIP spaces (**Picture 2**).

I was also able to get the learners' opinion of the site where the literacy activities take place and their answers are as follows

-What do you think concerning your Learning environment?

Talking about the study environment, I find that, out of 656 learners, 351 do not agree with their environment, 123 think it's OK, 60 disagree with the study environment, 60 still agree with their environment and just 62 people are very much in agreement with their learning environment (**Figure 7**). So we understand that if half of the respondents already think that there is a problem with the literacy environment, the government should look into it because it is a very important problem which can impact the engagement of adults into literacy program.

VII. Teachers

Contrary to what is said in the document that governs the national literacy program in Cameroon, literacy workers or literacy instructors do not have a predefined criterion at the national level. In most cases they are volunteers who, concerned about the future of their country, engage in the training activities of citizens; especially by teaching them reading, writing, calculations and sometimes post literacy activities. These teachers for the most part certainly go through training school which, should we say is not created by the government. It is a school that has been created by an individual and it focusses on training and coaching of literacy instructors. Often after their formation, literacy instructors face a lot of difficulties; whether for the creation and implementation of an adult literacy center or huge financial problems, because they are mostly without means and literacy activities as considered in Cameroon today by young adults is not an activity that one must spend money to benefit from. Once they hear about the opening of a literacy center, they all run to get trained but neglecting the financial parameters.

I even went to a center in Cameroon where it is the literacy instructor who buys notebooks, pens and all the necessary things for the literacy classes for her learners. When she tries to ask for a small fee or even to ask learners to buy the necessary material they need for their formation, they leave never again to return. That's why she decided to provide her learners with the necessary materials.

Despite all the difficulties encountered, teachers struggle to teach their learners in a better way. In almost all the centers I visited, many of the learners were favorable concerning the question about teaching methods used by their teachers.

-What do you think about the teaching method employed by your teacher?

Of the 656 learners, 358 strongly agree with the teaching method used by teachers in literacy centers, 60 people agree, 118 people think there is no problem with the teaching method 60 people disagree with teaching methods and the other 60 people strongly disagree with the teaching methods employed in literacy centers. When we try to calculate, we realize that the numbers of learners who agree with the teaching methods employed in their literacy centers are well above average, they are largely numerous compared to the number of people who think there is a problem with literacy techniques (**Table9**). As we can see, only 120 out of 656 learners

are dissatisfied with the teaching techniques used by instructors, and as I said above, for the most part, these problems stem from the fact that The language used in the center does not correspond to the language they have learned since childhood, which poses another problem related to the language of instruction.

VIII. Funding

The problem of funding in literacy centers in Cameroon remains a crucial and major problem. The Ministry of Basic Education, for example, is the ministry in charge of adult literacy in Cameroon. But when we see the share of the budget allocated to the literacy sector, we realize that it is very difficult to carry out literacy activities in Cameroon based on this budget. In the entire budget of the Ministry of Basic Education, the share allocated to literacy activities is only 1,5% of the total budget. This 1,5% is the entire budget allocated to the whole extended area of Cameroon for literacy activities, it must still be specified that if we take those 1,5% of the budget of the Ministry just to solve the problems of adult literacy in the city of Yaoundé it would be very insufficient. So what to do? Relying on international partners? this may be a solution for literacy centers, but the problem is that even by relying to international partners, there is no guarantee that funding will go to literacy centers who are supposed to be the main beneficiaries. Among all the centers I have been through in the Nfoundi Department, just a few centers in Yaoundé4 have benefited so far from a small teaching kit from the Ministry. When I speak of a small kit it is simply to make you understand that the material that has been given to the owners of literacy centers, according to them is very small not to say insignificant; because they say they have received only a few formats, some pens and some chalk.

It is true that there are international partners such as UNESCO, the World Bank, which also fund literacy activities. But with the policy that is used in Cameroon today, that is to say the policy of decentralization, tasks have been delegated to the different town halls, who are now responsible for receiving the various funds and handing them over to officials literacy centers. But since the decree was signed, the literacy centers until today do not yet benefit from the fruits of this decentralization. According to what they say, when they go to the town halls to ask questions concerning the financing of the centers, officials make it clear to them that the money

has not yet reached their level, and that once they receive money, they will distribute it to literacy centers. Then it becomes complicated for the instructors, because they teach mostly learners who have almost no means to pay for their training or who have a few means but who refuse to pay for their courses.

IX. Text books

The adult literacy program in Cameroon is not harmonized, especially since these literacy centers do not belong to the State. They are private centers created by individuals to help young Cameroonians in fighting against illiteracy. Talking of teaching materials, it should be noted that it is each head of center who manages to create his course materials, despite the fact that Government is suppose to support centers with teaching materials (Decree Number 2016/1247 / PM. (May 23, 2016)). There is no book in the program for adult literacy in Cameroon. But in literacy centers I realized that despite the lack of literacy materials from the Government, the teachers or owners of the literacy centers are doing pretty well, since the learners seem to be satisfied with the manual made available to them by their teachers (**Table 10**).

As we can see on **Table 10**, about learners' opinion on books or textbooks used to teach them, 81% of people are in favor of the teaching manual used in their literacy centers, while we have less than 20% who do not agree. If we go based on the majority, we can safely say that literacy textbooks used by teachers or literacy instructors meet the expectations of learners.

X. Relations between officials, literacy educators and learners.

X.1 Relations between officials and literacy educators

The majority of literacy instructors say that since the end of their training and the creation of their center, they have never received a visit from the staff of the Ministry of Basic Education in their centers. Many say they are left alone and sometimes do not know where to go when they encounter difficulties in their centers. For example, we have the following testimonials from some literacy centers instructors.

As an adult literacy teacher, have you ever been contacted by policy makers for any kind of revision or improvement of literacy policies?

- “Never. The department sent a representative here once and the goal was to identify the literacy centers that exist and carry out the activities. For the moment we are still waiting.”
- “No. So far not yet. We were contacted about a visit of the inspector, but it has not yet taken place given his busy schedule. We know that it will take place; but I do not think it will be to ask us what we think about literacy policy. It will be just a visit since they have the mission to go down to the field to check that the center really exists and that they conduct literacy activities.”
- “Not yet.”
- “Never.”
- “To this day, no”

Based on these answers from the literacy instructors, we can realize that adult literacy in Cameroon still has many steps to go through, as everything gives the impression that the decision-makers do not work in collaboration with literacy monitors.

X.2 Relations between officials and learners

I met adults in the field who do not even know which ministry they depend on, when I ask them they tell me clearly that they do not know to which ministry they belong and directly we understand that there is no contact between them and the Ministry of Basic Education which is the institution in charge of literacy issues for children and adults in Cameroon. I Asked them if they have been contacted by a ministry official, wanting to know how their courses are moving, they have had different answers but the majority have never been contacted even though they know that they are supposed to be contacted.

According to the diagram (**Figure 8: Relation between officials and learners**), 417 learners have never been contacted by a representative of the Ministry of Basic Education in order to find out how learners cope with classes, just 236 people say they have already been contacted. This means that the majority has never been visited by decision-makers.

For literacy learners, it is unacceptable for policymakers to develop policies that concern them, without asking them how they are faring in literacy centers. Their different points of view on the issue are summarized on (**Figure9: Do you think your opinion as adult literacy learner should be taken into consideration when officials (leaders) are taking any decision related**

to adult literacy education? (for exemple elaboration of the adult literacy books, the adoption of the language)

On **Figure 8 and Figure9**, we can see clearly that 91% of learners find it logical that they should be contacted by decision makers when it comes to adult literacy issues, as they are the main people concerned and are able to explain their needs. Thus, from their exchanges with the learners, the decision-makers can better find solutions adapted to the learners' difficulties.

XI. How monitors sensitize adults to attend literacy classes

Talking about how to motivate adults, I will show you the answers of some adult literacy educators, because each person uses his own specific method to bring the learners to be interested in the literacy program of the adults.

- “To motivate them, I always make them understand that in life nothing is lost. One of the main motivations is I. I always tell them that I went through this kind of school, the social schools. I did not go to classical school. It is true that I did not go there as an illiterate person, I already had a level, but I always make them understand that even if they know nothing; to come and learn how to read write and count is already an asset for them because nowadays we do not have to go to the market, buy things and being deceived by the trader at the moment when he must refund your currency; simply because you do not know how to count. Or in our day we do not need to go ask our neighbors to help us read our letters for us. When I talk about motivation I always remember a lady that has already graduated, she was here for 3 years and now she is in Europe; a 45 years old lady who arrived here thanks to our advertisements, having lost her household because she was not able to read. At the age of 45 she had never been to school, so she already had the hard wrist to write down the letters of the alphabet and even her own name she could not write. Her focal point when she arrived here was her trip to Europe and for that we focused on reading and writing according to the terms of the trip. Few times after, she was already able to write her name and to read airports indications and currencies exchange related vocabulary. 3 years after she left. When she started reading she called me every time to tell me that she received a phone message and she directly told me what the message said and it really put her in joy and confidence. And even

for withdrawals of currency she was already going to the bank all alone without needing any help from anyone to fill out the form. And that was an asset for her. I often use her story to educate others that there is no shame for someone who wants to learn to read and write; it is done for oneself and not for someone else. To the young girls I always say that marriage is good but nowadays men marry less and less women who cannot read and write. I captivate them much more with concrete examples and little stories that raise awareness”.

- “The first and most important way to sensitize them is to avoid talking about any fee when you want to get their attention. If you really want to have learners in literacy center, do not talk to them about money because once you say that they have to pay, everyone lose interest. The best way is to put in mind that what we are doing is a volunteer work before approaching people.”
- “It is very complicated because this program is not well known by the public. This is a program that is not very developed in Cameroon. Since the creation of this center, I am continuing to sensitize my neighborhood by talking to them about the new program of the Ministry of Basic Education which pay great attention to adult literacy; I tell them about the period of “school under tree” which has been corrected to a better way now through the new program set out by the Ministry. I tell them that with the new changing of the World, everybody have to be able to read and write in order to carry out his/ her activities. In short, I try to encourage them to attend the program. There are plenty of young people here in the neighborhood who cannot read and write. To motivate them tell them that we do not have the same curriculum as in formal schools; we have a typical program at the literacy centers and simply want them to know how to read and write, after what they will get a certificate at the end of the training signed by the Ministry of Basic Education. The mentioning of certificate motivates them a little.”
- “The methods used to motivate them is more sensitization. We do it by showing them the importance of being literate; since we have targets such as refugees, our brothers and sisters in the northern part of the country who are kind of lagging behind it terms of schooling. Not only do we show them the importance of literacy, but we discuss it with them without imposing anything to them. For example, in terms of enrollment and training fees, we go through negotiations with them. Since we realized that they do not already know the importance of what we are offering them, we cannot impose anything to them. There are

even times when we are forced to go to their homes drag them to come and learn. Well, maybe it's complicated because it's still the beginning.”

- “The first thing is to get them to understand why everyone should learn to read and write. They are adults, who are either called to have children, or already have children; it becomes more complicated for them to follow their children at home because they cannot read. So when the child brings home a homework assignment the parent is unable to help him. My first experience with this program was that, in my school where I teach, because I’m a teacher of primary schools; a parent came to school to register a child who does not have a birth certificate, I gave him a paper and a pen to write the name of his child; he could not write the name of his child. He pronounces but could not write; he did not let me know, but as a wise person, when the parent took the pen, he scratches his head to the left and to the right and begins to rub his cheeks; I understood what the problem was. So as not to continue to embarrass him, I quickly picked up the pen and the sheet I asked him to pronounce and then I write. There are many people outside who are in this same situation. I usually take these kind of example to sensitize my learners”
- “I am generally inspired by the success of predecessors. For example, the first ones who came here for classical literacy and who, after the first stage, entered into functional literacy is cited as example each time to those who are not interested into the program. I have a lady who was a mother of five and a housewife for more than a decade; she came here she did the classical literacy courses and then functional, and today she created her structure that seems to work very well since she is already driving a car. People like that I always take them as an example to motivate others. Initially, I had thought of going to churches to sensitize, but I ran into a difficulty because some pastors wanted me to be part of their church before they could allow me.”
- “Just awareness by telling them the importance of literacy. I always tell them that a person who does not know how to read is a sick person or is even worse than a sick person. I was told a story of a gentleman who carried an unopened letter in which it was written that he was to be killed and the note said: murder that gentleman who brings you this letter; So you see how someone, simply because he does not know how to read, carries his own death. And I often tell them that story. And also I start from an experience; a friend who invited me because she wanted to buy a piece of land. I arrived, the seller was a 26-year-old with whom

we discussed and arranged the price; but at the moment of filling in the papers, the buyer fills his part, the salesman was asked to fill in but he couldn't. He asked my friend to write everything and my friend asks him his name; to our surprise the name given by the gentleman did not match with the name on his identity card and there, we directly understood what the problem was; the gentleman could neither read nor write. It is from here that I took the initiative to get started in literacy and I like to tell this story to my targets. The other little story is that of a married woman whose husband managed to marry a second wife simply because the first did not know how to read.”

From the above stories, we can see that literacy educators in Cameroon use several means to sensitize adults to involve into literacy program.

Conclusion

At the end of this survey which focuses on Literacy practices in adult literacy centers in Cameroon and particularly in The Mfoundi Department, what I noticed is that literacy educators in those different centers are doing their best to increase the number of literate people in Cameroon. But they face so many difficulties which can be solved with the real implication of the Cameroonian government to work along with them. Despite their effort there are certain important key factors which are beyond their power, and can only get real solution through the real implication of the Government. Among those key factors we can mention the problems of teaching site; training and certification of literacy educators; funding of literacy activities; production of Text-books; Consolidation of relations between officials, literacy educators and literacy learners; Sensitization of illiterate adults through multi-channels.

References

- 1- MINEDUB. (Décembre, 2014). Politique Nationale de l'Alphabétisation, de l'Education non formelle et de la Formation en Langues. Yaoundé

- 2- Decree Number 2016/1247 / PM. (May 23, 2016). Setting the procedures for the exercise of certain powers transferred by the State to the municipalities in matters of literacy: *Supply of literacy materials in the form of kits. The provision of school infrastructure to support literacy courses.*
- 3- Decree Number 02012/268. (June 11, 2012). Organizing the Ministry of Basic Education (MINEDUB) entrusts the mission of fighting illiteracy to MINEDUB; with the creation within it of a Directorate and an inspectorate responsible for literacy, non-formal basic education and the promotion of national languages.

Figure 1 : Gender of participants

Figure 2 : Are you working for the government, private sector or self-employ?

Figure 3: Reasons why people are interested

Figure 4: Is the program interesting?

Figure 5 : What are the main discipline(s) your program offers?

Figure 6: Which discipline(s) do you prefer?

Figure 7: What do you think concerning your Learning environment?

Figure 8: Relation between officials and learners

Figure9: Do you think your opinion as adult literacy learner should be taken into consideration when officials (leaders) are taking any decision related to adult literacy education? (for exemple elaboration of the adult literacy books, the adoption of the language)

Table1: Distribution per gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	216	32.9	32.9	32.9
	Female	440	67.1	67.1	100.0
	Total	656	100.0	100.0	

Table2 (status of respondents): Are you a worker2

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	597	91.0	91.0	91.0
	No	59	9.0	9.0	100.0
	Total	656	100.0	100.0	

Table3: why do you find adult literacy program interesting?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0	298	45.4	45.4	45.4

Thanks to the program I'm now able to read, write and calculate	295	45.0	45.0	90
Thanks to the program I'm now able to communicate in other language than my mother tongue	4	.6	.6	90.9
Thanks to the program I have been able to develop my activity	59	9	9	100.0
Total	656	100.0	100.0	

Table4: why don't you find the literacy program interesting?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 0	534	81.8	81.8	81.8
It doesn't respond to my expectations	119	18	18	99.
I don't understand the lessons	1	.2	.2	100.0
Total	656	100.0	100.0	

Table5 . Why?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid It responds to my needs	418	63.7	63.7	63.7
I understand it better	178	27.1	27.1	90.9
Other reasons	60	9.1	9.1	100.0
Total	656	100.0	100.0	

Table6: How long have you being involve into adult litracy program

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than six months	358	54.6	54.6	54.6
	six months to two years	238	36.3	36.3	90.9
	Above two years	60	9.1	9.1	100.0
	Total	656	100.0	100.0	

Table7: How many time do you have classes per week

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	One time to two times	417	63.6	63.6	63.6
	Three times	179	27.3	27.3	90.9
	Four times	60	9.1	9.1	100.0
	Total	656	100.0	100.0	

Table8: what is the duration per class?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1hour	299	45.6	45.6	45.6
	2hours	297	45.3	45.3	90.9
	2 to 3hours	60	9.1	9.1	100.0
	Total	656	100.0	100.0	

Table9: About teaching method

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	358	54.6	54.6	54.6
	agree	60	9.1	9.1	63.7
	It's ok	118	18.0	18.0	81.7
	disagree	60	9.1	9.1	90.9
	Strongly disagree	60	9.1	9.1	100.0
	Total	656	100.0	100.0	

Table 10: What is your opinion concerning your Text books?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	297	45.3	45.3	45.3
	agree	60	9.1	9.1	54.4
	It's ok	179	27.3	27.3	81.7
	disagree	60	9.1	9.1	90.9
	Strongly disagree	60	9.1	9.1	100.0
	Total	656	100.0	100.0	

Picture1: Monitor's house serving as literacy center

Picture 2: Me (in brown), the literacy educator and her learners, in front of the literacy center.

Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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